

TRACES OF EARLY ALCHEMY IN INDIA.
RASĀYANA IN SOME KĀVYA AND KATHĀ TEXTS
WITH A NOTE ON CHINESE ALCHEMY

FABRIZIA BALDISSERA

ABSTRACT

This study starts by examining similarities and differences between medicine and alchemy in ancient India. It then proceeds to investigate the occurrence of motifs in the epics, and particularly in court literature, in satire and in the first Indian historical work. Its main concern is with India, but as some alchemical operations appear very similar to the Chinese ones, it tries to give also a general comparison of Indian and Chinese approaches to the subject. It is very difficult to establish the primacy in time of the Chinese ideas about 'inner alchemy', or of the Indian ones about Tantric 'alchemical' transmutation. There certainly were contacts, both by land and by sea. Both cultures used similar techniques of breath control, meditation and physical exercise. Both advocated the retention, or redirection, of semen. There were, of course, differences, which we shall try to point out.

ALCHEMY AND ĀYURVEDA

THE Indian medical and alchemical arts proceeded together for a long time, and even in *kāvya*, the ornate literature treated here,¹ they were often confused. *Rasāyana*, a term possessed of a multiplicity of meanings, often taken to mean alchemy and alchemical operations, in *Āyurveda*² qualifies the seventh branch of medicine, devoted to checking the process of physical and mental decay. In the beginning this was accomplished through herbal remedies, and only at a later stage through mineral or metallic preparations. In the medical sciences, even when they employed *rasaśāstra*, 'the scientific treatises, or science, of *rasa*',³ or 'of mineral-based pharmacy', including mercurial preparations, the emphasis was on *rogavāda*, 'therapeutic doctrine'. The two oldest *āyurvedic* treatises, dated from the first century BCE to the second century CE, prescribe only external remedies containing mercury. Mercurial preparations were to be ingested only starting from the *Aṣṭāṅga Saṁgraha* of Vāgbhaṭṭa the Ancient, in the sixth/seventh century CE.

¹ *Kāvya*, the most sophisticated genre of Sanskrit literature, rich of peculiar stylistic devices, meant for the appreciation of the learned.

² The traditional Indian medicine, the early texts of which date from the 1st century CE.

³ Other names for it were *rasavāda*, 'the doctrine, or exposition, of *rasa*', or *dhātuvāda*, 'the doctrine, or exposition, of *dhātus*, the constituent elements [of the world, and/or of the human body]'.

Alchemy, on the other hand, focussed on transmutation, either as *lohavāda*, ‘the doctrine of transmutation of metals’, or *dehavāda*, ‘the doctrine of transmutation of the body’, or elixir alchemy,⁴ in which the body of the alchemist would become immortal, or attain such a prolonged longevity as almost to achieve immortality.

The oldest meanings of *rasa*, a term already found in the Veda,⁵ which has an even vaster semantic field than *rasāyana*, was most likely ‘fluid’, ‘lymph’, ‘fluid essence’, ‘juice’, ‘water’. In medicine it means also ‘chyle’, the nutritive juice. In the Indian cuisine, the *rasas* were the six flavours, and in South India *rasa* still means ‘clear soup’. The *Nāṭyaśāstra*, a treatise on dramatic art dating in its final redaction from the fourth or fifth century CE, but containing material dating from the first century, used the term *rasa* in a culinary metaphor, where its meaning was taken to be ‘flavour’. Henceforth it was adopted in the technical meaning of ‘aesthetic flavour’,⁶ and also, with scholars of poetics or philosophers, it assumed the connotation of ‘aesthetic rapture’,⁷ the particular enjoyment given by a beautifully performed play, that could transport its audience to a different level of consciousness.

A very old mention of a mineral *rasa*, in *rasavidhā* or *rasapāka*, which is supposed to mean ‘smelted ore’, rather than refined mercury, in connection with gold mines, is found in the earliest Indian text of government, *Arthaśāstra* 2.12.2 and 2.13.3. Alchemy, on the other hand, interpreted *rasas* in the plural as ‘metals’, but in particular as ‘mercury’, the mineral ‘fluid essence’, seen as the transmuting agent *par excellence*, once refined through sixteen or eighteen alchemical processes. Another later meaning of *rasāyana* in fact is ‘elixir’,⁸ intended especially as ‘elixir vitae’. Its primary meaning, however, seems to be ‘the coming forth’, or ‘the extraction of *rasa*’.⁹

In the ancient Indian alchemical process a practitioner had to be initiated and had to perform ritual worship with the use of *mantras*¹⁰ before handling the alchemical substances. The alchemical texts describe the laboratory, the crucible (*musala*) and several organic and inorganic substances, among which are herbs, minerals, gems, metals, salts, and animal matter. The metals range from six

⁴ See also WHITE 1996, 52.

⁵ The ancient collection of scriptures; its dating is still controversial, and contemporary scholarship now tends to place them in the first millennium BCE.

⁶ See WARDER 1972, 24; BALDISSERA 2012, 344-47.

⁷ See GNOLI 1968, *passim*; WARDER 1972.

⁸ This term comes from the Arabic *al-iḫṣir*, but it seems to originate from the Greek *xerion*, ‘projecting powder’. But apparently ‘there is nothing about elixirs or macrobiogens in the documents of the Hellenistic proto-chemists’ (NEEDHAM 1974, v.2.71).

⁹ According to C. Wilkinson, see WHITE 1996, 73 and n. 133. And see below the *Mālaṭīmādhava* passage.

¹⁰ Several oral formulas present since vedic times; Tantric worship uses the same term *mantra* but gives it a different relevance and meaning, as in *mantrāyana* ‘the way of *mantras*’.

to twelve, and they undergo up to eighteen principal alchemical operations,¹¹ called *saṃskāras*, ‘perfecting’, or, ‘refining actions’.

Rasa, due to its fluid nature, was also interpreted as ‘semen’ and in particular, in alchemical texts, it was mercury, the semen of God Śiva. It may be thus useful to recall the āyurvedic science of the three *doṣas*, ‘humours’ of the body, the balance of which makes for health, as well as the general Indian notion of the five elements in connection with the body. The three *doṣas* are *vāta*, wind, *pitta*, bile, and *kapha*, phlegm. The latter contributes to the process of semen formation, growth, and nutrition. Śiva’s semen, in particular, is connected to the moon, repository of Soma, the essence of plants,¹² with rejuvenation processes¹³ being carried out mainly at full moon. Eventual contrasts were between the sun and the moon, or rather between the fiery strength of the sun and its earthly counterpart, Agni, fire, and the watery essence of the moon, and of its homologue Soma.¹⁴ In the laboratory the alchemist had to install a *rasaliṅga*, i.e. a Śivaliṅga¹⁵ coated with mercury (*rasa*), which would receive worship, and was usually made of an amalgam of gold and mercury, or of sulphur and mercury.¹⁶

Since very early times the five primary elements, called *bhūta* (or *dhātu*), were recognised as the bodily constituents. They were arranged as ether/space, *ākāśa*, to do with sound and with the ear; wind/air, *vāyu*, to do with touch and the skin; fire, *agni*, to do with light and the eye; water, *āpas*, to do with taste and the tongue; earth, *pṛthvī*, to do with smell and the nose.

The mineral substances used in Indian alchemy sometimes had telling names and myths attached to their place of origin. Mercury, *rasa*, was also called *sūta*, *sūtaka*, or *pārada* (from the land of the Parthians, Persian Baluchistan, or ‘the land of mercury’). Its principal reagent, regarded as the Goddess’s ‘sexual fluid’ or ‘uterine blood’, was sulphur, (*gandhaka*, ‘the perfumed one’¹⁷), or mica, (*abhrā* or *abhrākā*), perhaps the true origin of the arcane term ‘*abracadabra*’. Cinnabar, from which mercury is extracted, was called either ‘Chinese powder’, *cīnapiṣṭa*, as its largest deposits were in Yunnan, or else ‘*darada*’, from Daradadeśa or Dardistan, in Kashmir,¹⁸ or *hiṅgula*, connected with Hiṅglaj Devī, in Baluchistan (Pakistan).

¹¹ See also WHITE 1996, 145.

¹² See below.

¹³ These seem to be very ancient, as the rejuvenation of the *ṛṣi* (seer) Cyavāna through the offices of the Aśvins, the twin gods of medicine, is mentioned already in the *Rgveda*, the oldest Vedic scripture, dated around the middle of the 2nd millennium BCE. *Rgveda* v.78.56; vii.68.8; vii.71.5; x.39.4; x.59.1; x.61.2 (I wish to thank M. Gnoato who provided these references).

¹⁴ See also WUJASTYK 2004, 347-70.

¹⁵ The aniconic symbol of Śiva, a phallus with a *yoni*- (vulva)-shaped base (*pīṭha*).

¹⁶ This is synthetic cinnabar. In fact in Tamil, Malayalam and Sinhalese the term for cinnabar is *liṅga*. This usually means ‘phallus’, and also the ‘sign’ by which something is recognized.

¹⁷ Connected in alchemical texts with the myth of the Churning of the Ocean, found in the *Mahābhārata*, the largest Indian epic. The Goddess’s blood came to the surface, and it had a wonderful smell.

¹⁸ The mines nearest to India, beside Dardistan, were in Garmsir, in Afghanistan.

A fact that bears upon the antiquity of Indian alchemy is that Indian texts made a very early connection between immortality and gold, a metal perceived as stable and incorruptible. Gold as immortal, *amṛta*, and as the giver of long life was spoken of already in *Atharvaveda* XIX.26 (*āyusmān bhavati yo bibharti*, 'he who carries it [as an amulet] becomes long-lived'), while *Śatapathabrāhmaṇa* VIII.4.1.15 reads: 'Gold is light and fire is light, gold is immortality and fire is immortality'. In the ancient Sumerian epic of Gilgamesh,¹⁹ there was already a search for the herb of immortality, but it was not connected with gold. India and China enjoyed very early contacts, so that it would be very difficult to distinguish early Indian from Chinese contributions to each other's approach to alchemical matters.²⁰ The idea of using herbal remedies and aurification together occurred in China already in the fourth century BCE with Tsou Yen.²¹ The process of projection, through which a small amount of a potent chemical is added to a substrate, converting it all into precious metal, appeared in China at least by the end of the first century BCE.²² Chinese medical alchemy in the beginning prescribed herbal preparations to be eaten from golden plates produced by aurification; the direct ingestion of mineral remedies came later. The alchemists believed 'that it was possible to prepare, with the aid of botanical, zoological, mineralogical and above all chemical knowledge, drugs or elixirs (*tan*) that would prolong human life beyond old age, rejuvenate the body and its spiritual parts'.²³

The originality of Indian and Chinese alchemists consists in their having, at some point in their history, abandoned the laboratory operations of transmutation of the external substances involved in aurification, aurifiction²⁴ or the preparation of elixirs, in order to work directly on the body of the practitioner by using only the substances already present within the body.²⁵ In India this procedure was very similar to that used by some esoteric Tantric practitioners. In a correlative of the Chinese inner alchemy, *nei tan*, it is from the substances present within their own frames that Indian Tantric adepts, *sādhakas*, (also called yoga²⁶ adepts, yogins), who aspired to immortality or to the attainment of special *sid-*

¹⁹ Its composition started around the middle of the 3rd millennium BCE.

²⁰ The name for cinnabar, *cīnapiṣṭa*, already suggests that it was imported from China.

²¹ See NEEDHAM 1974, v.2.11. (I am using throughout his old spelling for Chinese terminology).

²² See NEEDHAM 1974, v.2.13.

²³ See NEEDHAM 1974, *ibidem*.

²⁴ An imperial edict of 142 BCE forbade the minting of 'false yellow gold' (NEEDHAM 1974, v.2.12).

²⁵ In China 'external alchemy', *wai tan*, that used very strong mercurial elixirs, often compounded with lead and arsenic, after causing the death of probably four emperors and innumerable princes, ceased in the 8th century. We do not possess many data about mercurial poisoning leading to death in ancient India, but the practice of 'religious alchemy' with mercurial elixirs stopped there in the 13th/14th century (see WHITE 1996, p. 55). A limited form of it was re-absorbed by Āyurveda, that still employs very refined mercurial compounds in its *materia medica*. The terminology of 'external alchemy', however, and the worship rites connected with it, remained the same in both countries even when bodily substances replaced the mineral ones.

²⁶ They employed the breathing and physical techniques later known as Haṭhayoga.

dhis, ‘magical faculties’, extracted an elixir that, pushed through an ascending process within the body channels and *cakras* (wheels [of energy]), would end up and be stored in the cranial vault. If their wish, however, was not for power and enjoyment (*bhukti*) in the world, but for final liberation (*mukti*), then they should push that stored essence upwards to make it exit through the *brahma-randhra* (the suture between the cranial bones on top of the head) and join the last *cakra* situated a little above the head. In this way some adepts capable of extreme effort would be able to reach *jīvanmukti*, ‘liberation while still alive’. In a similar way in the alchemical process the reversal of the natural downward flow of bodily sexual juices was believed to generate a reversal of the ageing process. The Chinese spoke of a similar reversal of the flow of fluid essence (semen and saliva) along the spinal cord, and their term for it was ‘making the Yellow River flow backwards’. Their aim was to reach ‘material immortality’, and be able to live with an ethereal body together with the Immortals.

The Indian power-seekers not interested in reaching liberation, on the other hand, could obtain one or all of the special *siddhis*,²⁷ such as the power of flying, whose acquisition in this manner was presented for the first time²⁸ in Bhavabhūti’s drama *Mālatīmādhava*.²⁹ This seems to be the first literary work that brings together tantric practice, alchemy, and the cult of ancient terrific goddesses who haunted cremation grounds and required blood sacrifices from their power seeking devotees.³⁰

Another word connected with *rasa* and *rasāyana* is *rasarasāyana*. This term apparently refers to a mythical notion of alchemical technique, which however is not explained. The first occurrence of *rasarasāyana* (or just *rasāyana*, perhaps?) according to White may be in *Mahābhārata*³¹ 1.165.10, in the description of the wish-fulfilling cow of sage Vasiṣṭha, ‘which in addition to milk gives “the six flavours and the fluid ambrosial elixir” (*saḍrasam cāmytarasam rasāyanam*)’.³²

Many other literary texts describe different types of alchemists and alchemical processes, often defining them as quacks engaged in fake experiments. In Daṇḍin’s *Daśakumāracarita* (‘The adventures of the ten princes’), of the seventh or eighth century, the seventh book, the adventures of Prince Mantragupta, presents a king Jayasimha duped into believing in reinforcing or rejuvenating

²⁷ Different lists of six or eight, and up to twenty-six magical faculties, *siddhis*, are found at first in Buddhist texts. A late common gnomic verse says: *aṇimā laghimā prāptiḥ prākāmyam mahimā tathā/ ṛṣitvaṃ ca vaśitvaṃ ca tathā kāmavasāyitā/* ‘The faculty of becoming as small as an atom, that of becoming weightless, that of obtaining anything, then that of having an irresistible will, that of becoming extremely large, that of exerting supremacy, that of subduing (or, fascinating) [others], and that of dwelling where one pleases (including moving through the air)’.

²⁸ At least in the literature discovered so far.

²⁹ See below.

³⁰ SANDERSON 1985, n. 89 observes that the *Jayadrathayāmala* gives a very thorough explanation of the process (see below).

³¹ The oldest Indian epic; its final redaction is attributed to the 4th or 5th century CE.

³² WHITE 1996, 53 and n. 15. The grammar does not seem to work, but establishing the text here is actually often conjectural.

magic. He wanted to conquer a young woman held prisoner by a *rākṣasa*³³ and was persuaded to plunge at midnight in the waters of a ‘miraculous’ lake, capable of giving him the power to resist the *rākṣasa*. But that was only a trick to have him killed. Similar charlatans appear also in the *Kathāsaritsāgara*³⁴ of Somadeva, and in a few satirical works. The alchemical texts, on the other hand, are written around the tenth³⁵/eleventh century, and there was also oral transmission through the siddhas, travelling ascetics who did not often use Sanskrit and rarely wrote books. The medieval siddha alchemists used alchemical knowledge, *haṭhayoga* techniques of breath control and bodily postures, as well as Tantric worship involving the use of sexual fluids.

THE WITHERING OF THE MOON AND OF KINGS (RĀJAYAKṢMAN)
THROUGH SEXUAL EXCESSES

From the iatrochemical point of view, due to the alchemic/religious connection of *rasa*-mercury with male seed, and especially with Śiva’s immortal semen, *rasāyana* accompanied by *vājīkaraṇa*, sexual rehabilitation therapy, was thought to be the best remedy for *yakṣman*, ‘consumptive sickness’, often occurring in kings as *rājayakṣman*. Kings had to be fertile in order to further and increase their lineage, and also on a symbolic plane, as the belief was that a king’s first wife was the Earth itself, and a king’s sexual vigour thus was needed to impregnate the soil magically and make it yield fruit. Excessive indulgence in sex, however, could bring about a dangerous exhaustion of semen and generative ability. This call to moderation in sexual activity – an activity deemed laudable *per se* – was also a Taoist concept: semen should exit one’s body only for procreation. Otherwise it had to be redirected towards the top of the body, in a manner reminiscent of the Tantric reversion of the flow.³⁶

One of the oldest occurrences of the motif of dispersion of strength through excessive love-making, recalled in several alchemical texts, is the myth of King Moon, Candradeva, and Dakṣa’s curse. The motif of the moon’s waxing and waning in connection to Soma³⁷ is already alluded to in the *Ṛgveda*, and is then narrated in the *Mahābhārata* and in several *purāṇas*.³⁸ In the *Mahābhārata* story

³³ A type of demonic being, ‘from whom one should protect (*rakṣ*) oneself’.

³⁴ See below.

³⁵ It seems that the oldest one may be the *Rasahrdayatantra* of Govinda, of the 10th/11th century.

³⁶ Taoism maintains, however, that sex should be an enjoyable activity, especially for women (who thanks to their more refined nature did not need to restrain themselves), but also for men: by applying pressure in specific areas, there were ways of achieving orgasm also without emission of semen, as explained for instance in *Su Nu Ching, The Immaculate Girl Canon*, quoted by NEEDHAM, 1956, vol. II, 146 following, and NEEDHAM 1974, vol. V, part II, 34-35 and 149-151.

³⁷ The god presiding to the sap of plants and connected with the moon phases. It is also an ancient inebriating drink – whose identity is still unknown – used by the gods and their human sacrificers in the solemn sacrificial sessions of Soma.

³⁸ *Rgveda* x.85.2 (but without any allusion to Dakṣa); *Mahābhārata* xvi, 35.

Candradeva is married to the twenty-seven asterisms (*nakṣatras*), daughters of Dakṣa and Pañcajanī, under the condition that he treat them all equally. Candra instead dallies only with his favourite star Rohiṇī. Dakṣa, incensed at Candra's continuous disregard for the other *nakṣatras*, and for his wishes, curses him to wither and die.³⁹ But as Soma, of which the moon is the repository, is wasting, the herbs fail to grow, their juices dry up and become tasteless. The world suffers and the gods miss their ambrosial drink. They then approach Dakṣa and ask him to withdraw his curse. This cannot be, but Dakṣa can mitigate its effect: for half the month Soma (identified here with Candradeva) shall wane progressively every day, and for the following half month it shall wax every day. Finally, in the sacred *tīrthā* ('crossing', and 'pilgrimage place') called Prabhāsa ('splendour'), where the river Sarasvatī mingles with the Ocean, Candradeva, having regained his lustre, becomes whole again.

At a later period the speculations, begun in the first *Upaniṣads*, on the identity⁴⁰ between different things and processes in the macrocosm and the microcosm of human activity, were carried on in all fields. The case of King Moon was related to man, and still later, in the alchemical texts, transmutations in metals were equated with transmutations within the human body.⁴¹ As it takes twenty-eight days for a new moon to restore its splendour as full moon, in the same way it was believed that it would take a man twenty-eight days of a special diet to restore his spent semen. Mercury (*rasa*), once identified with the semen of Śiva, was to be one of the main ingredients in this cure. In some cases, however, the consumptive disease (*yakṣman* or *rājayakṣman*, royal consumption) was so serious that it could not be cured, or the remedy itself proved fatal.

A similar instance is narrated already in *Mahābhārata* 1.7.96, vv. 57-58, of Vicitravīrya, son of King Śantanu and Satyavatī, ancestors of the Kurus. Vicitravīrya marries two beautiful sisters, Ambikā and Ambālikā. The wives adore their handsome husband, and he is happy to frolick with them for seven years:

*tābhyāṃ sahā samāḥ sapta viharan pṛthivīpatiḥ /
vicitravīryas taruṇo yakṣmāṇaṃ samapadyata / 57 / /*

³⁹ According to later interpretations perhaps it was the continuous love-making with Rohiṇī which eventually sapped his sap (see also WHITE 1996, 24, n. 40).

⁴⁰ On the principles of identity and substitution being the mental *habitus* of Indian thinking see MICHAELS 2004, 5-12 and 334-336.

⁴¹ Both Chinese and Indians, for instance, having observed the incorruptibility of gold as compared to other metals, tried to create some 'potable gold' capable of arresting physical and mental decay. In *Rasārṇava* 17.165-66, a text of the 11th century CE, it is said *yathā lohe tathā dehe kartavyaḥ sūtakaḥ sadā / samānaṃ kurute devi praviśan dehalohayoḥ / pūrvaṃ lohe pañkṣeta tato dehe prayojayet*, 'Mercury (*sūtaka*) should always be used in the same way in metals as in the body. Having entered into metal and in the body, O Goddess, it does the same thing. First it should be tested in metal, and afterwards employed in the body'. The Chinese prescribed equally to test the elixirs first on metals, then on man.

v. 57. In their company that lord of the earth spent seven years;
Vicitravīrya, [though still] young, died of consumption.

*suḥṛdām yatamānānām āptaiḥ sahā cikitsakaiḥ /
jagāmāstam ivādityaḥ kauravyo yamasādanam // 58 //*

v. 58. Even though his friends made efforts together with capable physicians,
the Kuru scion, like a setting sun, went to the abode of Yama.⁴²

As for the Kurus lineage, the most unfortunate thing was that Vicitravīrya did not father a child, having exhausted his seed in pointless sex, like many other heroes in this epic, who had trouble fathering their own progeny and had to resort to external help, human or divine.

The same type of fatal consumption plagued young king Agnivarman in the nineteenth canto of the *Raghuvamśa* of Kālidāsa, India's most famous writer from the fourth to fifth century CE. Agnivarman did not care for governance, but spent all his time enjoying himself in the harem. Both his disregard for government and his sexual binges were remarkable. He lived by night and slept during the day (xix.34), until in the end a consumptive sickness carried him off.

*gauravād yad api jātu mantriṇām darśanaṁ prakṛtikāṅkṣitaṁ dadau /
tad gavakṣavivarāvalambinā kevalena caraṇena kalpitam // 7 //*

xix.7. If out of reverence for his counsellors he gave a sight (*darśana*)⁴³ [of himself], which had been long desired by his subjects, this was performed by the mere dangling of a foot through the opening of a window.

*taṁ pramattam api na prabhāvataḥ śekurākramitum anyapārthivāḥ /
āmayaḥ tu ratirāgasambhavo dakṣaśāpa iva candram akṣinot // 48 //*

xix.48. Other kings were not able to conquer him because of his [reputation for] prowess although he was careless [through vice], but a disease (*āmaya*) born of [his extraordinary] passion for love-making made him waste away like the curse of Dakṣa consuming the Moon.

dṛṣtadoṣam api tan na so 'tyajat saṅgavastu bhiṣajām anāśravaḥ /

xix.49 (first hemistych) Even though the damage (*doṣa*) could be seen he did not leave his addiction, nor did he follow the advice of his physicians...

*tasya pāṇḍuvādanālpabhuṣaṇā sāvalambhagamanā mṛdusvanā /
rājayakṣmaparihānir āyayau kāmāyānasamavasthaya tulām // 50 //*

xix.50. His royal consumptive sickness (*rājayakṣman*), which gave him a pale face, allowed him [to wear] but very few⁴⁴ ornaments, had him walk only supported [by servants], gave him a soft voice, rendered him similar to the condition of a lovelorn person.

⁴² The god of Death.

⁴³ To give *darśana* from the part of an august person means 'to concede an audience', and the duty of a king was to give daily audience to his subjects, as he had to administer justice.

⁴⁴ Or, 'small', 'light in weight'.

*vyoma paścimalāsthithendu vā paṅkaśeṣam iva gharmapalvalam /
rajñi tatkulam abhūt kṣayāture vāmanārcir iva dīpabhājanam // 51 //*

xix.51. While the king was suffering with consumption, his family appeared like the sky with the moon in her last digit; like a summer puddle with only mud left [in it]; or like a lamp having a dwarfed flame.

(Agnivarman's illness was kept secret, then he was secretly buried, but luckily managed to leave the queen with child).

ALCHEMICAL TERMINOLOGY IN DIFFERENT KĀVYA TEXTS

The earliest occurrence of a term for mercury, *pārada*,⁴⁵ in *kāvya* (ornate fiction), is found in the novel *Vāsavadattā* of Subandhu, attributed to the second half of the sixth century. It is part of a simile, in which the heart of the lover is deemed to be so anxious and unsteady, that 'it cannot stand still even for a moment, just like mercury (*pārada*)'.

The same text also presents for the first time Tārā, a Buddhist deity, doubly connected with alchemy: in her Tibetan form of Ekajaṭā, 'Having one lock of hair', she was supposed to be the consort of mercury, identified with Bhairava Yamāntaka, 'Slayer of death'. She was also known as Vajratārā, 'Diamond Tārā', and in some later alchemical texts, alchemist Nāgārjuna is said to have brought Tārā to India.⁴⁶

Next, *rasāyana* appears in the two novels of Bāṇabhaṭṭa from the seventh century, in the historical romance *Harṣacarita*, about the life of Bāṇa's patron, King Harṣavardhana of Kanauj (606-647), and in the work of fiction *Kādambaṛī*, which upon the death of Bāṇa was completed by his son Bhūṣaṇabhaṭṭa. In Bāṇabhaṭṭa mercury (*rasa*) appears also as a substance *per se*: Vindhya tribals are said to paint their swords with mercury, both in *Harṣacarita* 415 and in *Kādambaṛī* 393.

The fifth book of the *Harṣacarita* narrates the impending death of Harṣa's father:

5.176. '...the prince (Harṣa) in distress of mind rejected the betel, and when the sun inclined to setting, summoned all the physicians in private, and with a despairing heart inquired what steps under such circumstances should be taken. "Your highness", they answered, "reassure yourself: in a very few days your father will be reported restored to his proper self and pristine condition". Among their number, however, was a young doctor of Punarvasu's race named **Rasāyana**, a youth of about eighteen years of age, holding an hereditary position in the royal household, in which he had been cherished like a son by the king. He had mastered the Āyurveda in all its eight divisions, and, being naturally of an acute intellect, was perfectly familiar with the diagnosis of diseases. He now

⁴⁵ It probably originates from *pāradaśeṣa*, which means either Persia or 'the country of mercury'.

⁴⁶ WHITE 1996, 65.

stood silent and tearful with downcast looks. Being appealed to by the prince, “Friend Rasayana, tell me the truth, if you see anything at all unpromising”, he replied “To-morrow at dawn, your highness, I will state the facts of the case”.... 5.178. Hearing from distracted young princes standing before him an indistinct murmur “Rasayana, Rasayana”, he asked “ Well, friends, what of Rasayana?”, whereat they all at once became silent. Being further pressed, however, they with sorrowful reluctance explained: “Your highness, he has entered fire”. The prince became (ashy) pale, as if scorched by an inner fire, and his grief-blinded heart, torn up by the roots, refused to be steadied. “A noble man”, he thought, “would rather not be, than like an ordinary person utter unwelcome and distressing words. His generous nature, maintained in trying circumstances, has like unadulterated gold acquired a greater brilliance by entering fire”⁴⁷.

Later a passage in the sixth book mentions ‘royal consumption’ brought about by dangerous drugs found in *rasarasāyana*, here taken as ‘elixir of life’:

6.224. ‘Some quack doctors, the virtues of whose medicaments had been celebrated through many different individuals, brought *rājayakṣman* upon Ganapati, son of the king of Videha, who was mad (*abhiniveśin*) for the elixir of life’.⁴⁸

At 8.283-284 Bāṇabhaṭṭa tells the ancient story of a monk Nāgārjuna,⁴⁹ friend of a Śātavāhana⁵⁰ ruler, who had presented the king with an elixir in the shape of a gem (*maṇi*) that he had received from the king of the *nāgas*.⁵¹ Thanks to the elixir the monk had lengthened his life and that of his kingly friend of many hundreds of years.⁵²

There are two external witnesses to the story, who would however advance the date of the (or of an) alchemist Nāgārjuna to a later period. The first is the account of the famous Chinese Buddhist pilgrim Hsuan-tsang, who was at the court of Harṣa and mentioned a Bodhisattva Nāgārjuna so proficient in medical alchemy that he had compounded a pill through which he had prolonged the life of both himself and the king for several hundreds of years.⁵³ The second is the later testimony of the eleventh century al-Biruni

⁴⁷ Translation by E. B. Cowell, F. W. Thomas 1897.

⁴⁸ The last sentence could also be rendered as ‘ who was absolutely devoted to the *rasa* (‘fluid’, or ‘mercury’) of *rasāyana*’.

⁴⁹ For the dearth of Nāgārjuna figures found in alchemical, Buddhist and Tantric literature, and for a Tibetan ‘explanation’ of that variety, see WHITE 1996, 66-77. Often the different figures, philosopher and alchemist, are conflated, like in the *Harṣacarita*.

⁵⁰ The Śātavāhana dynasty ruled in Andhra from the 1st century BCE to the 2nd CE. If the Nāgārjuna mentioned by Bāṇabhaṭṭa is the Madhyāmika philosopher, the Śātavāhana king was Gautama-putra Śātakarṇi, to whom Nāgārjuna wrote an epistle, the *Suḥṛllehika*, ‘Letter to a dear friend’.

⁵¹ Theriomorphic mythical figures of the netherworld, similar in shape to mermaids and tritons.

⁵² A very similar story about a Nāgārjuna and a king called ‘Long lived’ is narrated in the *Kathāsaritsāgara* (see below).

⁵³ See NEEDHAM 1974, vol. v, part 3, 162, and WHITE 1976, 67-68. WHITE reports also a meeting of the same Chinese pilgrim with a Brahmin disciple of Bodhisattva Nāgārjuna, who appeared to be only thirty, but was actually 700 years old.

who mentions an alchemist Nāgārjuna who had lived about a hundred years before himself.⁵⁴

Alchemy is even more present in the *Kādambaṛī*, where an old Draviḍa ascetic,⁵⁵ who looked after a terrifying temple of goddess Caṇḍī, appeared to have quite ruined his body through the application of the wrong medications and substances. A charlatan (*kuvādin*) gave him a magical collyrium (*kuvādidattasiddhāñjana*), so noxious that he was blinded in one eye. He seemed to be prey to mercurial hallucinations, and was plagued 'by an untimely fever induced by badly compounded mercurial preparations' (*asamyakṛtarasāyanān īākālajvareṇa*). He also had a collection of manuscripts on jugglery, Tantra and Mantra, with the characters written on palm leaves in fumigated letters of red lac (*dhūmaraktālakṭakāṣaratālapattrakuhakatantramantrapustika*); he had written down the doctrine of Mahākāla (Śiva), which is the ancient doctrine of the Mahāpāśupatas;⁵⁶ he talked about alchemy (*dhatuvāda*) and treasures, he spoke of having learnt the magical spell (*mantrasādhana*) for becoming invisible, and told thousands of wonderful stories about Śrīparvata.⁵⁷ He had often employed woman-subduing powders on old female ascetics from foreign countries who stayed [at the temple].

The alchemical import of *Kādambaṛī* is also shown by its continuous reference to the moon and its phases, personified in the figure of Candrapīḍa ('Embraced by the moon'), one of the main heroes of this magical fable, whose real nature is discovered only in the surprise ending of the story. Candrapīḍa is a young prince of exceptional virtue and qualities, who dies of a broken heart when he hears of the tragic end of his best friend, because he understands that he shall not be able to be united with his beloved Kādambaṛī in his present life. Kādambaṛī, the daughter of a celestial nymph (*apsaras*), born from the Ocean, is also of the essence of the *amṛta*, the elixir of immortality. Thanks to her contact, Candrapīḍa's body, though motionless and deprived of breath, does not decay. As Kādambaṛī does not leave his side, the prince's body daily acquires an increasing glow, that becomes brighter with the coming of spring. On the day of the spring festival Kādambaṛī, filled with longing and almost maddened by the god of Love, secretly embraces Candrapīḍa as if he were alive. And as with Snow White and Sleeping Beauty, her kiss of love, like an elixir of immortality (*rasāyana*), managed to revive the young prince, who in reality was the Moon God in disguise, lifeless because of a curse. The whole work is filled with similes referring to the moon or the moon glow, or to its second birth from the Ocean, and to *amṛta*, the nectar of immortality churned from the Ocean, like signs sown to hint at the denouement of the plot.

⁵⁴ WHITE 1976, 76, from Indian, Chinese and Arabic sources concludes that there were at least three separate Nāgārjunas who lived in different epochs.

⁵⁵ BĀṆABHAṬṬA 1973, 67.

⁵⁶ A Tantric śaiva sect, connected with the Śrīsāila (also called Śrīparvata) mountain in Andhra.

⁵⁷ See above.

About a hundred years after Baṇa, Bhavabhūti's play *Mālatīmādhava*, from the eighth century, presents the first occurrence of an extraction (*ākarsaṇa*) of the liquid of immortality, *amṛta*, from a person's own body.⁵⁸ Here it is called *pañcāmṛta*, the 'quintessence', or the essence of the five elements (i.e. the body constituents). What is perhaps even more relevant is that this might be the first mention⁵⁹ in Sanskrit literature of the six *cakras*, (wheels [of energy]),⁶⁰ present within the body (*aṅgacakra*). The extraction is performed by the female *kāpālikā*⁶¹ Kapālakuṇḍalā, pupil of an Aghora guru, prior to a blood sacrifice to a terrific goddess invoked in a subsequent hymn as Cāmuṇḍā or Karālā.

Prelude to act v, [Stage directions]: 'Then appears, flying through space in a terrific blaze, Kapālakuṇḍalā (*tataḥ praviśati ākāśayānena bhīṣaṇojjvalā Kapālakuṇḍalā*)

(Kapālakuṇḍalā): *śaḍadhikadaśanāḍīcākramadhyasthitātāmā*
hṛdi vinihitarūpaḥ siddhidāś tadvidām yaḥ /
avicalitamanobhiḥ sādhakair mṛgyamāṇaḥ
sa jayati pariṇaddhaḥ śaktibhiḥ śaktināthaḥ / 1 /
iyam idānīm aham
nityanyastaśaḍaṅgacakranihitam hṛtpadmamadyoditam
paśyantī Śivarūpiṇam layavaśād ātmānam abhyāgatā /
nāḍīnām udayakrameṇa jagataḥ pañcāmṛtākarsaṇād
aprāptotpatanaśramā vighaṭayanty agre nabhombhomucaḥ / 2 /

v.1. The god whose self abides in the middle of the circle (*cakra*) of the sixteen veins (*nāḍī*, channels), he who, when his form is placed in their hearts, grants *siddhi* to those who know that, who is searched for by [his] devotees (*sādha*) who have unwavering minds, may he, the Lord of Śakti, surrounded by energies (or: 'by *śaktis*'), be victorious.

v.2. seeing that self that has the form of Śiva, perpetually placed in the circle (*cakra*) of the six limbs touched by *nyāsa*,⁶² and which has risen (*udita*) in the middle of the lotus of the heart by means of absorption, I have come.

⁵⁸ See SANDERSON 1985, n. 89: 'Yoginīs, Śakinīs and other female obsessors suck life from their victims into themselves as an offering to their regent Mahābhairava enthroned in their hearts. This extraction [*ākarsaṇa*] is "imitated" by the worshippers of Bhairava and Kālī: see *Jayadrathayāmala* 3, fol. 184 v. 5-8; *Brahmayāmala-Picumata*, fol. 10 v. 2-4. These extracted "nectars" are the fuel of *Kapālakuṇḍalā*'s magical flight in Bhavabhūti's play *Mālatīmādhava* Act. V. 2. The method of extraction mentioned there [*nāḍīyudaya*] is described in minute detail in *Jayadrathayāmala* 3 above'.

⁵⁹ As Tantric texts are so poorly dated it is difficult to say if there are previous mentions of the *cakras* in early Tantric literature. According to D. Goodall (personal communication) the 72,000 blood vessels mentioned in *Bṛhadāraṇyakopaniṣat* 2.1.19 could have become the 72,000 *nāḍīs* (tubes, veins) of later Upaniṣats, and the Saiddhantika literature used the term *granthi* instead of *cakra*, but only knew five of them. He also suggests that the *Viṇāśīkhatantra*, that mentions the *cakras* as well as the *granthi*, may be earlier than the *Mālatīmādhava*, but says that there is very little firm evidence of this.

⁶⁰ They are the *mūlādhāra* (anus), *svādhiṣṭhāna* (genitals), *maṇipura* (navel), *anāhata* (heart), *viśuddhi* (throat), *ājñā* (between the eyebrows).

⁶¹ An ascetic who carried a *kapāla*, skull, as an alms-bowl.

⁶² *Nyāsa* is a particular form of worship consisting in a special way of touching one's own limbs.

Gradually through the raising in the channels (or: 'veins'), because of the extraction of the five ambrosias of the world (or: 'of my moving body', *jagat*), I have not obtained exhaustion in my ascending [in the sky] while I tear mist and clouds in front [of me]'.⁶³

Kapālakuṇḍalā, like many *kāpālikas*, is connected with the ancient mountain of the siddhas Śrīśailam, in Andhra Pradesh (called Śrīparvata in Buddhist sources), even today a seat of Śaiva cult.⁶³ There she takes the heroine of the play Mālatī, the designated victim of her sacrifice. Luckily in Śrīśailam at the time there was also another woman who had obtained special *siddhis*, the *yoginī* (yoga adept) Saudāmanī. Her own search for power, however, did not seem to require blood sacrifices. Possessed of the same magical faculty of flying, she rescued Mālatī, checked the desperate acts of her friends, and transported Mālatī's young lover Mādhava.

In ix.52 Saudāmanī shows Mādhava and his friend Makaranda her skill in flying, and taking Mādhava with her disappears saying:

*iyam idānīm aham
gurucaryātapastantramantrayogābhīyogajām /
imām akṣepiṇīm siddhim ātanomi śivāya vaḥ / 52 / /*

ix.52 (Saudāmanī): 'Now I shall unfold, for your good, this magical power (*siddhi*) of transporting [people through the air], born of the constant practice of yoga and of [the use of] Tantra and Mantra,⁶⁴ of ascetism, and of practising with a teacher'.

Mention of *rasāyana* as 'elixir vitae' occurs also in the *Āgamaḍambara* of Bhaṭṭa Jayanta, who was the adviser (*amātya*) of King Śaṅkaravarman (883-902) of Kashmir, and whose work was instrumental in banning the most heterodox religious sects from the country.

Act Two - text, p. 43, after v. 17:

*tataḥ praviśata ekanīlapatapravyṛtau gayantau stripuṃsau vibhavānusareṇa
vā bahūni tathāvidhāni mithunāni gāyanti / /
jayai muṇi nīlambaraṇāho jeṇa samio bhavasamvaragāho
jasu bhaavām tuha sāsana nokkham pijjai kim pi rasāṇasokkham /
bhava buñjijjai itthiasukham paraloe pāvijjai mokkham / /
so sijjhai saṅraḍā laṅghijjai saṃsāraḍā /
to aṇṇe je puṇa āsamā tāṇa nībamdahu āsa mā /
parisosijjai dehaḍā mokkhami puṇa samdehaḍā /
sikkhājoe kāi viḍhappai purusu paravvasu parisammappai /⁶⁵*

⁶³ Śrīśailam since the 7th century saw a surge in the dedication of temples to Śiva Siddheśvara, ('Lord of the siddhas') and even before that time was frequented by *kāpālika*, *pāśupata* and *kālamukha* ascetics. From the 12th century on, however, the dominant group was the *vīraśaiva* sect.

⁶⁴ *Mantrayoga*- could also translate as 'the knowledge of magical spells', or 'of the magical spells of Tantra'.

⁶⁵ The adepts of the Nīlāmbara sect, of which very little is known, here speak a form of Apabhraṃśa, a middle Indo-Arian dialect.

([stage direction]: ‘Then enter a woman and a man, covered in a single black robe and singing, or many couples, if possible).

Victory to the sage (*muṇi*) Nīlāmbaranātha,⁶⁶ who has relieved the disease/obsession of keeping life within bounds.

One who follows your novel teaching, O Blessed Lord, drinks the unique bliss of the elixir *vītae* (*rasāyanasaukhyam*, pracrit *rasāṇasokkham*).

In this life he revels in [making love to] women, in the next world he achieves deliverance.

The body bears fruit, transmigration is crossed over.

Have no faith in schools other than this: the body is completely emaciated, [and] liberation is still uncertain.

What is procured in the pursuit of training? Man is finished in someone else’s grasp’.⁶⁷

A connection of *rasa* (mercury), *rasāyana*, *siddhas*, and *kāpālīka* ascetics (and/or sextons) appears also in Kṣemiśvara’s tenth century *Caṇḍakauśika* (*Angry Kauśika*).⁶⁸ The story hails from the puranic myth of King Hariścandra and the anger of the sage Viśvāmītra Kauśika, whom the king had unwittingly interrupted during a rite. The king offered his kingdom in reparation, but the sage, unassuaged, asked for another *daḥṣiṇā*⁶⁹ as well. The king decided to earn it by becoming a slave in Varanasi, and as the sage was not placated when even his queen, rushing before the king, had sold herself as a slave, the king declared that he would sell himself even to a *caṇḍāla*.⁷⁰ God Dharma immediately appeared disguised as a *caṇḍāla* and bought the king.

Act iv takes place in a cremation ground: the duty of Hariścandra was to take the blankets from the dead⁷¹ and give them to his new master. Dharma enters disguised as a *kāpālīka*, (term which here may mean ‘a sexton’, rather than ‘a skull-bearing ascetic’). The king greets him as a Mahāvratin.⁷² At Act iv, v. 31 it appears that the *kāpālīka* possessed several magical powers (*siddhi*): control over a Vetāla⁷³ and a thunderbolt (*vajra*), possession of magical pills (*guṭikā*), collyrium (*añjana*) and foot salve;⁷⁴ command over Daitya⁷⁵ women; knowledge

⁶⁶ Nīlāmbaranātha, ‘The Nath (Lord) of the blue/black blanket’, presumably leader of a group of very merry ‘ascetics’ devoted to love making in public (though under their blanket/mantle). The play records their expulsion from Kashmir at the hands of King Śaṅkaravarman (*nīla* actually means ‘blue/black’).

⁶⁷ Translation by C. Dezsö, in DEZSÖ 2005.

⁶⁸ See LORENZEN 1972, p. 49, 57-59, p. 87. I did not manage to procure a Sanskrit text of this play.

⁶⁹ Usually a ritual fee for celebrating a rite or a sacrifice.

⁷⁰ A member of the most despised outcaste group, contact with whom was considered extremely impure.

⁷¹ Again, contact with anything connected with death or corpses is considered extremely impure and inauspicious.

⁷² A particular type of ascetic that has taken a solemn vow. See BALDISSERA 2005, 147-148, and n. 285 (supplied by Sanderson).

⁷³ A type of malignant spirit who can be subjugated and used as a magical means of transport.

⁷⁴ Another magical form of transport.

⁷⁵ Demon-women, reknown for their beauty.

of *rasāyana* (elixir of life) and of alchemy (*dhātuvāda*). Then, leaving the king to guard these things, the *kāpālīka* left to look for a great treasure of magical mercury (*siddharasa*) that could grant immortality, as he explicitly says in Act IV, v. 34:

iv.34. 'Driving away death through its use and at once attaining the path to the immortal world, the Perfected Ones (*siddhas*) enjoy themselves on the peaks of Meru, where the wishing tree bears clusters of blossoms'.

The *kāpālīka* offers that magical mercury of immortality to the king, but he refuses to accept it for himself, being a slave, and asks him to give the treasure to his master, the *caṇḍāla*.

FRAUDULENT ALCHEMISTS AND PHYSICIANS IN SOME SATIRICAL WORKS
OF KṢEMENDRA, A POLYMATH OF ELEVENTH CENTURY KASHMIR

In Kṣemendra's *Deśopadeśa*'s third canto, v. 32, mercury (*rasa*) is one of the substances employed by an old harlot to regain her lost looks:

matsyayūśarasair dāsī ghṛtakṣīrapalāṇḍubhiḥ /
priyam parāṇmukham iva pratyānayati yauvanam // 32 / /

III.32. Through fish, soup, mercurial preparations, ghee, milk and onions the harlot (or 'slave') takes back her youth, which, like a lover, had kept its face averted from her.

At *Deśopadeśa* III.47 she is also said to be an alchemist, (*dhātuvādinī*), and endowed with the qualities of a *siddha*.

Deśopadeśa's fourth canto is devoted to the bawd, *kuttanī*. iv.3 sais that, like a *kāpālīka*,⁷⁶ she is distinguished for drawing blood from men, and the term employed for 'drawing' is *ākaraṣaṇa*, the same used by Kāpālakuṇḍala in *Mālatīmādhava*, and explained in several tantric texts.⁷⁷

The fifth canto is about an impoverished man about town, the *viṭa*, usually reduced to be a love-messenger between lovers and courtesans. Here v.27 describes the *viṭa* as a quack who poses, among other things, as an alchemist. It is also particularly interesting in that it connects alchemy with *yogaśāstra* (the treatises on yoga) and the knowledge of caves (where ascetics dwell, or where mineral ores are found), as well as with the preparation of perfumes, which was also a prerogative of alchemists – and of ex-beaux.

rasāyanair bilajñānair yogaśāstrair asaṅgataiḥ /
gandhayuktikathābhiś ca mugdhān bhunkte jaradvītaḥ // 27 / /

v.27. An old *viṭa* profits of naive people through elixirs (of life), knowledge of caves, the science of yoga, non-attachment, and talks about the preparation of perfumes.

⁷⁶ A term that could mean both a *kāpālīka* (skull-bearing) ascetic, or a sexton from the cremation ground.

⁷⁷ See n. 58 above (from SANDERSON 1985, n. 89).

Deśopadeśa's eighth canto gives a description of various people, and three verses describe the alchemist:⁷⁸

*jarayā jīrṇaśāriraḥ kāsaśvāsprayāsahataśaktiḥ/
vrajati rasāyanasiddhaḥ svagurum vṛddho'py aśeṣāyuh / / 20 / /*

VIII.20. His body used up by old age, his potency (*śakti*) destroyed by the troubles of coughing and asthma, even though he is old and has no life-span left, the alchemist (*rasāyanasiddha*) goes to his teacher.

*mūṣāmukhavistīrṇair bhūrisuvarṇair karomi sampūrṇam/
nijajanam aparam ca rasair ity uktvā nirdhano mriyate / / 21 / /*

VIII.21. 'Through the mercurial preparations (or 'elixirs') spread out of the mouth of my crucible (*mūṣā*) I shall make my own people and others full of abundant gold', so saying he dies in utter poverty.

*paryantātīsāre lagne vṛddhasya sūtasiddhasya/
śuddhir dehamalānāmi jātety upajāyate harṣaḥ / / 22 / /*

VIII.22. When dysentery has completely consumed him, there is joy for the old alchemist (*sūtasiddha*),⁷⁹ [as he thinks]: 'A purification of my body's impurities has occurred'.

Ḳṣemendra's *Narmamālā* III.17 mentions a *rāsāyanī*, 'alchemist', without describing him, but he is shown in the company of the very despicable devotees of a dubious guru of the Kaula sect. The people mentioned immediately before and after him are respectively a *mantravādin*, 'reciter of *mantras*' and an *indrajalīn*, 'conjurer, illusionist', all of them obviously considered quacks and swindlers.

Narmamālā describes the Kaula guru himself as a dabbler in alchemy: at III.74 he is asked to provide *pauṣpaka* 'oxide of brass, green vitriol', a substance used in alchemy to rejuvenate old people, for an old man married to a young woman, 'so that the wife may become enamoured of [her husband] who has acquired sexual might (*śakti*)'.

Ḳṣemendra's *Samayamātrkā* presents a bawd who has changed her identity several times. At the end of her life she pretends to know alchemy (*dhātuvādām*), saying:

*varṣaṇam me sahasram gatam adhikatarām vedmy aham dhātuvādām
siddho me vākprapañcaḥ karatalakalitam traipuram kāmattvam / ...*

1.103 (first hemistich). 'A thousand years have passed on me, I know the most excellent alchemy, I have perfected the unfolding of eloquence, the essence of desire (*kāmattva*)⁸⁰ is carried in the palm of my hand', [...].

⁷⁸ These three verses, like all the different groups of verses in this canto, are preceded by a caption which might have been provided by the copyist of the manuscript. This one says: *dhātuvādī*, 'alchemist'.

⁷⁹ *Sūta* is another term for 'mercury'.

⁸⁰ ḲṢEMENDRA 1961 mentions *kāmattva* also in his *Kavikaṇṭhābhāraṇa* 1.1 and 1.14, and a *kāmattvika* appears in the series of despicable devotees of the debauched Kaula guru in *Narmamālā* III.17, BALDISSERA 2005. See personal communication of Sanderson at n. 292, explaining that *kāmattva* in that

RASĀYANA AND ALCHEMY IN SOMADEVA'S KATHĀSARITSĀGARA

The eleventh-century *Kathāsaritsāgara*, completed in 1081, contains innumerable stories⁸¹ of magical talismans or *siddhi*-granting objects,⁸² and three important stories concerned with alchemy, one about aurifaction (VII.1., vv.80-91), the other two about the employment of *rasāyana* for rejuvenation (VII.6., 42-115) or prolongation of life (VII.7., 9-60). In the last story the elusive figure of an alchemist Nāgārjuna appears. All three stories concern kings, and all occur in book VII, *Ratnaprabhā*.

The first story, one of metallic transmutation or laboratory alchemy, concerns the brave and generous King Vikramatūṅga, ('Peak of valour'), who once propitiated Agni (god of fire) through his valour by offering his own head. Once a young boy asked for a private audience, and told him that he had a magical powder, *cūrṇa*, given him by his guru, and a means, *yukti*, capable of transforming copper into pure gold. The king had some copper brought and the boy melted it but though he had thrown on it three times his special powder, no transmutation occurred. Vikramatūṅga, possessed of magical sight through the grace of Agni (fire), the element (*bhūta*) connected with sight and the human eye, saw that an invisible *rākṣasa* had stolen the powder each time the boy tried to throw it. Thus the king took the powder and threw it on the molten copper, that immediately turned into gold (*kanakatām āgat*⁸³).

The second story concerns King Vilāsaśīla ('Lover of pleasure'), who asked his court physician to be rejuvenated. The physician said that he should dwell alone for eight months in an underground room (*bhūgrha*), taking some medicaments.⁸⁴ The king did not listen to his counsellors, who warned him that formerly those powerful elixirs (*rasāyāni siddhāni*) were obtained through asceticism (VII.6.52), but that at their present times they did not exist any more, or had an adverse effect (VII.6.53). The king went into the chamber, assisted only by the doctor, who six month later, seeing that his patient looked even older than before, killed him, and substituted in his place a young man who looked a bit like the king. Every day he showed him, from afar, some of the king's subjects, and the women of the harem, so that he became used to them, and the people saw that he was changing into a young man.

context (as here) could mean both a *siddhi* by which one can subject anyone to one's desires, or, jokingly, 'the essence of lust'. Sanderson adds: 'for the *śākta kāmattva* and its power see *Tantrāloka* 2.165c-173b; *Vāmakeśvarīmata* 5.1, 4.34-46'.

⁸¹ Many of which are much older.

⁸² In *Kathāsaritsāgara* VIII.6. v. 75, for instance, the Brahman Guṇaśarman is given an eye ointment (*añjanā*) that makes him invisible.

⁸³ See also SOMADEVA 1993, 391.

⁸⁴ The old treatment for King Moon was *kuṭīpraveśa*, 'entering into a hut'. The patient was shut into the innermost chamber of the hut, called *garbhagarbham*, 'womb of the womb', from which he was expected to exit reborn. See WHITE, 1996, 26.

There are two interesting points here. The first one is the South Indian āyurvedic remedy of the ‘underground house’, or ‘secluded hut’. The doctor keeps a patient secluded in a room akin to the womb⁸⁵ where the foetus had his three humours in perfect balance. And that calls to mind also the hut where the sacrificer is secluded in his period of *dikṣā*, ‘initiation’. The second point is the scientific attitude and disbelief of the king’s ministers in the powers of *rasāyana* as a rejuvenating elixir.⁸⁶

The last narration, of iatrochemical import, involves King Cīrāyus (‘Long lived’) and his minister Nāgārjuna, born of a particle of a Bodhisattva, who knew all herbs and had prepared a magical elixir, *siddharasāyana*, which gave him and the king absence of old age and long life (VII.7.11). But at the death of his youngest son the minister, thanks to his ascetic power, started preparing ambrosia (*amṛta*) with certain substances. As he was nearing the end of the compound, Indra saw him and sent the twin medical gods, the Aśvins, to check him (VII.7.15), enjoining him to stop the preparation of ambrosia (*amṛtasādhana*) (VII.7.19), if he did not wish to be cursed. So he said: ‘I shall interrupt the work of ambrosia (*amṛtakriyā*) (VII.7.25); in five days it would have been completed (*siddha*) and I would have liberated people from old age and death’. Then he buried the almost ready ambrosia. The story continues: the heir apparent of Cīrāyus, Jivahāra (‘Who takes away life’), was told by his mother that his only chance of becoming a king was to kill Nāgārjuna. As the latter was a generous man who never refused a supplicant, the prince had only to ask him for his head. Nāgārjuna accepted, but his neck, hardened by the elixir (*rasāyana*) (VII.7.45), could not be cut but broke several swords. The king came to stop him from offering his head, but the minister said that he had offered his head already ninety-nine times (VII.7.47), and this was the hundredth. So his head was cut after he put a special powder (*curṇa*) on the sword of the prince (VII.7.50). ‘Thus the destruction of death started by Nāgārjuna was not tolerated by the gods’ (VII.7.59).

AN ALCHEMIST IN THE FIRST HISTORICAL INDIAN WORK

Kalhāṇa’s *Rājataranginī*, written in the twelfth century, reports the feats of a great alchemist (IV.211-216; 246-247) at the court of Lalitāditya Muktapīḍa of Kashmir (725-761).⁸⁷ It was Caṅkuṇa,⁸⁸ defined as a Tuḥkhāra, ‘a person coming

⁸⁵ This also recalls some ancient Chinese medical practices, whereby the patient, by entering a secluded structure, was supposed to become pristine as a newborn baby. This reproduces a Taoist practice of believing to be capable of entering a double gourd (cp. STEIN 1942, 57-58, citing the *Yun-ki Ts’i-tsen*).

⁸⁶ This is a rather early example of disbelief, as the practice continued.

⁸⁷ KALHĀṆA gives an earlier date, 700-736, but comparison with Chinese documents suggests that it is better to take it forward of about twenty-five years; see STEIN 1989 note at IV.45.

⁸⁸ According to STEIN 1989 (IV.211 n.), the term might be the reproduction of a Chinese appellation indicating a particular title.

from Tokharisthan, or Bactria'⁸⁹ in IV.211. Caṅkuṇa gained an important position, as he became the head counsellor of King Lalitāditya and dedicated two buddhist monasteries, *vihāras*, in the two capital cities of Kashmir. His wife and his son-in-law are also mentioned (IV, vv. 212, 216) as people who dedicated public buildings. His son-in-law was a physician (*bhīṣak*), while Caṅkuṇa's brother was the alchemist (*rasasiddha*) Kaṅkaṇavarṣa, 'Rain of gold' (v. 246). Caṅkuṇa's gift in aurifaction is described at v. 247:

*sa rasena samātanvan kośe bahusuvarṇatām /
padmākara ivābjasya bhūbhṛtobhūc chubhāvahaḥ // 247 //*

v. 247. Creating a lot of gold by means of mercury (*rasa*) in the [royal] treasury, he provided prosperity to the king like a lotus tank to a lotus.

The two following verses (vv. 248-252) relate that through a magical gem, *maṇi*, Caṅkuṇa was capable of parting the waters of some large streams, so that the king's army could ford them, and also, later, by using a different talisman, of restoring them to their normal flow. There is something interesting about the special alchemical power of Caṅkuṇa: the king wishes to be given the gems able to command the rivers, and the counsellor says that they could only perform their job when kept in his own hand. The king however obtains them by exchanging them with a large statue of the Buddha, that Caṅkuṇa installs in one of the *vihāras* he had built.

At the death of the king, Caṅkuṇa says that the alchemical power, *rasasiddhir*, given to him in order to increase the king's treasury, has also disappeared.

*sasṛje yasya kṛtino daivataiḥ kośavṛddhaye /
rasasiddhir akasmān me yasmāt sāstam upāgatā // 363 //*

v. 363. 'Therefore that magical faculty of mercury (*rasasiddhi*) that had been granted by the gods for the increase of the treasury of that virtuous one has all of a sudden vanished from me'.

Occurrences of the term *rasāyana* used figuratively as 'elixir for the eye', or 'for the ear' is found in very numerous, later *kāvya* texts. The ones chosen here are, up to the eleventh century, the oldest and those that mention alchemical substances or processes in the most significant way.

INDIA AND CHINA

This overview of the presence of alchemical images and stories in ancient Indian fiction has also recurred to Chinese witnesses, and to similar Chinese conceptions. It does not seem possible to determine exactly the timing and the extent of reciprocal influences between China and India concerning alchemical

⁸⁹ The interest of certain Buddhist families from Bactria for Indian religious and scientific texts, even during Islamic domination, is investigated in VAN BLADEL 2011 (I wish to thank D. Wujastyk for the reference).

lore (apparently the Chinese had the largest cinnabar deposits, but were happy to learn some techniques from India), but it is very interesting to observe similarities and differences in their approach. Generalizations are very reductive, and the number of texts dedicated to alchemy in both countries is extremely large, so that an assessment can only be a very loose approximation. Indian adepts seemed to desire either power in this world or liberation from it, possibly during their lifetimes. The Chinese were speaking of material immortality, which seems a concept very near to the Indian one of the *jīvanmukti*, the person who has achieved liberation during his own life. If one looks only at India, at first Indian alchemy seems completely original in positing that the main substances for the alchemical operations, mercury (*rasa*) and mica (*abhrā*, *abhrakā*) or sulphur (*gandhaka*), correspond to the sexual fluids of Śiva and the Goddess. A perusal of texts⁹⁰ on the inner Chinese alchemy (*nei tan*), however, shows a very similar picture, influenced by Taoism. The Indian concepts maintain their originality in that they take into account two divine beings, intended as they are perceived in Tantrism. In Chinese alchemy, on the other hand, one finds a male principle, Yang, and a female principle, Yin, that apply to all men and women as perceived in Taoism. While Yang is related to mercury, in the same way as Śiva, Yin is usually related to lead, rather than to mica or sulphur.⁹¹ Another difference is that, besides ‘reversing the flow’ by a special manner of breathing, sexual techniques involving the redirection of semen and other physical activities joined with meditation, the Chinese adopted also other means. They advocated an increased production and retention of saliva⁹² the flow of which was equally redirected with special exercises, and used techniques of exposition of the body to the rays of the sun (for males) or of the moon (for females). However, what appears truly remarkable is that in India and in China the male and female principles appear reversed in their symbolism related to water and fire (or fluid and fire). In India the Goddess, and therefore the female principle, is perceived as fiery and dangerous.⁹³ In China on the other hand male Yang is fire, and female Yin is water and possesses its yielding qualities – even though in the relative ordering of the elements water wins over fire.⁹⁴

⁹⁰ Mainly NEEDHAM 1974, v.2. *passim* and PREGADIO 2011.

⁹¹ But red lead has to do with sulphide.

⁹² Saliva and sexual juices were the principal substances employed for the transmutation of ‘inner alchemy’, and it is interesting to recall that our contemporary allopathic medicine has recognized the great contribution of saliva in boosting the immune system.

⁹³ The fiery Indian goddesses were assuaged by terrible offerings of blood and human flesh from the cremation ground, as well as of mixed sexual fluids.

⁹⁴ In the opening passage of an early Han text, *Su Nu Ching*, the Immaculate Girl says: ‘...Now woman is superior to man in the same way as water is superior to fire. And those who are experts in the art of sex are like good cooks who know how to blend the five tastes into delicious dishes. Those who know the Tao of the Yin and Yang can fully achieve the five pleasures. Those who do not know it die untimely, without ever having experienced sexual joy...’, NEEDHAM 1974, v.5:192.

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